

ORAL TRANSLATION AS A SPECIAL TYPE OF SPEECH-INTELLIGENT ACTIVITY

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Annotation: The article is devoted to develop a methodology for the formation of the basic competence of an interpreter in the logic of a situational-contextual approach while integrating the principles of personal-activity, contextual-competence, communicative-cognitive, intercultural, scenario-situational approaches, creating a system of pre-translation and translation exercises as a tool for teaching oral translation activity, conducting experiential learning, analyzing the results of experiential learning, as well as in the practical application of the results of this study.

Key words: approach, content, language, communication, research, linguistic material, literary translation, material,

There are many definitions of the term "translation". From the point of view of the communicative approach, it is interesting to interpret the concept of "translation" as a type of activity, an act of intercultural interaction, taking into account the purpose, subject, sender, recipient, means. conditions of communication and information transfer. The goal of translation as an activity is to ensure interlingual interaction and to recreate the communicative value of the original message, that is, to meet the needs of communicators of different language cultures for natural communication and to achieve consensus. According to A.F. Shiryayev, the concept of translation as an activity and the product of this activity should be clearly distinguished: the researcher considers translation as a process from the perspective of a psycholinguistic approach. The purpose of translation activity is "to produce speech statements according to a certain social order" [162]. R.K. Minyar-Beloruhev understood translation activity as a type of speech activity, the purpose of which is to convey a message between communicants with different codes [1].

When talking about the specific features of translation as a type of speech-thinking activity, it is necessary to emphasize the point of view of N.K. Garbovsky suggests a "complex network of relationships with the environment" emphasizing time and specific space [2].

R.K. In his Annotated Dictionary of Translation Terms, Minyar-Beloruhev defines interpretation as "a concept that unites all types of translation, including oral design, including independent translation types such as consecutive interpretation, simultaneous interpretation, and sight interpretation. " describes [65]. As you can see from this laconic definition, unfortunately, it does not cover all the features of the implementation of the translation process, the main focus is on the nature of the flow of the interlanguage transcoding (oral) speech process. It also highlights, in the author's opinion, the main subtypes of interpreting, which we will need to return to a little later in this paragraph to discuss in more detail. However, this definition, like the first one, does not give a complete picture of its characteristics in terms of the situational characteristics of oral translation, which is very important for this study.

The third definition of the review N.K. According to Garbovsky, translation activity is "a public function of communicative mediation between people using different language systems, which is carried out in the process of psychophysical activity of a bilingual person to reflect

reality on the basis of his individual abilities as a translator. for the equivalent purpose of making a transition from one semiotic system to another, i.e. the most complete, but always partial transfer of the system of meanings contained in the original message from one communicant to another" [30]. Such a definition seems to be the most complete and most accurately reflects the specific features of the oral translation process. Based on this interpretation, it is possible to consider the activity of interpreting from the point of view of its orientation to the situation. It is clear that the translation, even the most adequate, is only the interpretation of this meaning by the translator. Such a location of the translation places it in the semantic field of the concept "interaction" and emphasizes that interpretation is a process of interaction, in which the interpreter himself is an integral part of the interaction. In addition, attention is paid to the role of the surrounding reality (situation) in which the translation process takes place.

Interpreting activities, N.K. According to Garbovsky, it takes place in the context of a single oral presentation of the original message, while the author notes that the process can be accompanied by several interventions without the possibility of returning to the already started translation, without the right to edit it.[30].

The fourth definition refers to the field of didactics of oral translation, E.R. Porshneva, he is G.V. Chernov considers the activity of oral translation not only speech (as in I.A. Zimnyaya), but speech and thinking. Interpreting is a multi-functional type of inter-linguistic and inter-cultural communication, which consists in understanding and transmitting the content of the text created in the language of one culture by reshaping it in the language of another culture. It should be noted that the activity of oral translation is aimed at the production of a specific text product, and the translator is fully responsible for its informative accuracy. In his activities (both verbal and written), the translator communicates with representatives of two languages and cultures in a common situation for them, plays the role of an intercultural mediator [3, p. 18].

Among the types of oral translation, it is possible to distinguish sequential, paragraph-by-phrase, simultaneous translation, whispering, translation from a sheet, audiovisual translation. This is a classification of interpretation types by professional translators at the university, and the teacher's special attention is directed to teaching consecutive interpretation to undergraduate (IV year) and specialist (V year) students. Simultaneous interpreting is often studied as part of additional education programs and courses. That is why this research is aimed at forming the basic competence of the translator in consecutive translation.

References:

1. Миньяр-Белоручев, Р.К. Французский язык. Курс устного перевода: учебное пособие для вузов / Р.К. Миньяр-Белоручев. — М.: Экзамен, 2005. — 160 с.
2. Гарбовский, Н.К. Лекция 15. Дидактика переводческой деятельности [Электронный ресурс]. — Режим доступа: <https://medium.com/@estimsu> (дата обращения 11.03.2019)..
3. Поршнева, Е.Р. Междисциплинарные основы базовой лингвистической подготовки специалиста-переводчика: дис. ... д-ра пед. наук: 13.00.08 / Поршнева Елена

Рафаэльевна. — Казань, 2004. — 425 с.

4. Кулдошов У. Инглиз ва ўзбек тилларида конверсивлик ва антонимлик ҳодисаси //Иностранная филология: язык, литература, образование. – 2021. – №. 3 (80). – С. 67-73.
5. Daminov N. K. SIMULTANEOUS TRANSLATION INTERPRETING AS A MODERN TYPE OF TRANSLATION //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2023. – Т. 4. – №. 2. – С. 77-81.
6. Daminov N. K. Using Interpreting Strategies in Teaching Simultaneous Translation //European Multidisciplinary Journal of Modern Science. – 2022. – Т. 12. – С. 40-47.
7. Daminov N. Using some strategies in simultaneous interpreting process //E3S Web of Conferences. – 2023. – Т. 381. – С. 01104.
8. Kasimova A. N., Rakhmonova G. N. THE USE OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS AS HEADLINES OF MASS MEDIA //Евразийский журнал социальных наук, философии и культуры. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 3. – С. 153-158.
9. Kasimova A. N., Nurullayeva D. S. H. NEOLOGISMS IN MODERN ENGLISH AND THEIR TRENDS IN WORD FORMATION (BASED ON TEXTS IN THE MEDIA) //Евразийский журнал социальных наук, философии и культуры. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 3. – С. 130-133.
10. Nosirovna K. A. et al. NEWSPAPER STYLE. THE TRANSLATION ISSUES OF LEXICAL UNITS AND WORD COMBINATIONS IN NEWSPAPER TEXTS //Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal. – 2022. – Т. 10. – №. 2. – С. 285-287.
11. Xidirovich N. X., Daminov N. Q. SINXRON TARJIMON NUTQIGA QO ‘YILADIGAN TALABLAR //IJTIMOIY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 4. – С. 21-27.